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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

these particles interact with biological systems remains limited. The detection, monitoring, and characterization of nanoplastics in biological contexts, especially in human cells, is a significant challenge due to their size and low environmental concentrations. This study aims to address this gap of imaging and detecting nanoplastics at relevant concentrations within human cells using Surface-Enhanced Raman Spectroscopy (SERS). SERS is an analytical technique capable of providing molecular-level information with high sensitivity and spatial resolution, making it suitable for detecting and visualizing nanoplastics at low concentrations in complex biological environments. To investigate the viability of SERS as a tool for detecting nanoplastics internalized in cells at low concentrations (<100 µg/L), we used macrophages (THP-1 PMA-differentiated) as a cell model. The cells were sequentially exposed to spherical AuNP, followed by exposure to polystyrene (PS) nanoplastics (100 nm) as test nanoplastics. SERS measurements were conducted with a 633 nm laser wavelength in a WiTec Alpha 300 R confocal Raman microscope. Raman mappings collected with enhanced vibrational signals from SERS enabled the identification of AuNP and PS nanoplastics within the cellular environment, confirming the uptake of both particles by the cells. Our findings demonstrate the effectiveness of the SERS technique for detecting and intracellular localization of nanoplastics in human cells and potentially across various cell types. This dual capability for detection and imaging underscores the utility of SERS in studying cellular interactions with nanoplastics. These results contribute to a foundational understanding of nanoplastic behavior, interactions within cells, and their potential health impacts. The authors thank the São Paulo State Research Support Foundation (FAPESP) (Process 2024/07778-1) for financial support to the project.

1.09.P-Mo060 Linear Polyethylene Terephthalate Oligomers Toxicity in Human Primary Cells and Interactions with Biomolecules

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Side-products of PET polymerization reactions are cyclic and linear oligomers of PET, recently recognized as novel non-intentionally added substances in food (NIAS) and classified as poor data chemicals. Risk assessment of PET oligomers is challenging due to their size, number, isomerism, complexity in structure, and lack of analytical standards. The great heterogeneity in size and structure of PET oligomers calls for a systematic approach in risk assessment and hazard identification. The aim of our study was to synthesize and characterize physicochemical properties, to investigate solubility in common solvents and food simulants, as well as protein, DNA and cellular interactions of a series of linear methylated and non-methylated PET oligomers (monomer, dimer and trimer). Our results show striking differences in the properties of PET oligomers in relation to size and end-group chemistry (methylated vs. free carboxyl- vs. hydroxyl-). Solubility in food simulants decreases with increase in methylation and the number of aromatic rings. Linear PET oligomers show little to no toxicity in a wide range of concentrations tested in primary cells. All linear PET oligomers tested readily interact with food and serum proteins, and with salmon sperm DNA. Our results point to the importance of size and end-group of PET oligomers in chemical risk assessment: size and methylation of the oligomer strongly contribute to the observed cellular and molecular effects of tested compounds. PET oligomers binding to DNA prompts further research on the toxicological relevance of the observed interactions. This study was supported by the Serbian Academy of Sciences and Arts Project F-26; IMPTOX European Union s Horizon 2020 research and innovation program (grant number 965173); the Ministry of Science, Innovation and technological development of the Republic of Serbia (Contract number: 451-03-68/2024-14/200168). This research was supported by the Science fund of the Republic of Serbia, Grant No. 7275, Exploration of PETase side activity of digestive enzymes of human gastrointestinal tract acting on micro- and nanoplastics: mode of action and products characterization XPACT and Region Stockholm (ALF project FoUI-986234), The Swedish Cancer and Allergy Foundation, The Swedish Asthma and Allergy Association's Research Foundation (Number: F2022-0011); The Swedish Heart-Lung Foundation (Number: 2021042), The Konsul Th C Bergh Foundation, The Magnus Bergvall Foundation and The Karolinska Institutet s Research Foundation Grant.

1.09.P-Mo061 The Toxicity of Microplastics Explorer (ToMEx) 2.0 Database – A Unique Compilation of Microplastics Effect Measurements for Environmental Risk Assessment

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